

TAILORING OUTREACH FOR DIFFERENT STAKEHOLDERS

Who? Audience: local and state government, policymakers, funders

Why? Customizing engagement matters

Different stakeholders have different priorities, communication styles, and levels of influence. Tailoring outreach ensures messages resonate and drive action.

Key considerations for tailored outreach

Understand Audience Priorities

Align engagement approaches with stakeholder interests.

Cultural Competency

Adapt materials and language to be inclusive and accessible.

Power Dynamics Awareness

Ensure communities have meaningful roles in decision-making.

What? Outreach Strategies by Stakeholder Type

Policymakers & Government Agencies

- Present data-driven narratives with personal stories for impact.
- Engage through advisory boards and legislative roundtables.

Funders & Philanthropic Organizations

- Showcase measurable impact and community success stories.
- Invite funders to community-led events to witness engagement firsthand.

Business & Private Sector

- Highlight economic benefits of equity-focused policies.
- Foster corporate-community partnerships that align with CSR goals.

FOR A DEEPER DIVE

- **Chapter 1:** [Establishing & Mobilizing an Effective Community-Engaged Program](#)
- **Chapter 7:** [Policy and Practice](#)

ACTION STEPS

- Map stakeholders and tailor messaging accordingly
- Use storytelling to humanize data and research